

Facile synthesis of (*E*)-7-hexadecen-1,16-olide (ambrettolide)

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Abstract : (*E*)-7-Hexadecen-1,16-olide (ambrettolide), having musk-like odour being used as a fixative in perfumery industry. It was synthesized from *threo*-aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid) by simple procedure.

Keywords : Facile synthesis, ambrettolide.

Lac is a product of commerce, yielding resin, dye and wax. It is derived from lac insects cultured on specific trees called lac hosts. The principal constituent acid of lac resin is aleuritic acid (~35%), naturally occurring in *threo*-form. It is being used for syntheses of a number of compounds like ambrettolide, exaltone etc. particularly for use in perfumery industry. (*E*)-7-Hexadecen-1,16-olide (ambrettolide, **6**), a macrocyclic lactone having musk-like odour, used as a fixative in perfumery industry had been synthesized earlier from *threo*-aleuritic acid (**1**)¹ (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid), the major component acid of lac involving multiple reaction sequence resulting in low yield (42–44%)^{2,3}. Here, a more simple synthesis of compound **6** from **1** is reported, with improved yield.

threo-Aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid (**1**), m.p. 100–101 °C) was esterified with dry methanol containing BF₃.Et₂O to yield methyl aleuritate⁴ (m.p. 73–74 °C), which on treatment with dry acetone containing conc. sulphuric acid followed by oxidation with KMnO₄/AcOH² afforded half-ester (**2**). Preferential reduction of the half-ester with LAH/THF⁵ followed by deacetonation by boiling with 10% H₂SO₄ gave the expected *threo*-isoaleuritic acid (7,8,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid (**3**) which on treatment with imidazole, chlorodiphenyl phosphine and iodine in 1,4-dioxane for 2 h yielded 16-hydroxy-(*E*)-7-hexadecenoic acid (**4**) in quantitative yield. It was esterified as above to afford methyl 16-hydroxy-(*E*)-7-hexadecenoate (**5**). Distillation of **5** with MgCl₂.6H₂O resulted in the formation of ambrettolide (**6**).

Experimental

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by TLC.

Methyl aleuritate : It was prepared (10.0 g, m.p. 72–73 °C) from *threo*-aleuritic acid (11.0 g, m.p. 100–101 °C) adopting the procedure reported in literature⁴); ν_{max} 3250 (-OH), 1738 cm^{-1} (-COOCH₃) (Found : C, 64.0; H, 10.5. Calcd. for C₁₇H₃₄O₅ : C, 64.1; H, 10.6%).

16-Methylhydrogen-7,8-isopropylidenedioxy hexadecanedioate (3) : Methyl aleuritate (10.0 g) was stirred in pure dry acetone (25 ml) containing conc. sulphuric acid (0.2 ml) for 1 h and then left for 2 h at room temp. It was neutralised with 30% aq. KOH (2 ml). Finely powdered KMnO₄ (7.7 g) and glacial AcOH (2 ml) were added in installments during 1 h, with stirring which was continued for another 3 h, during the last hour the mixture was heated under reflux. The solution was filtered, acetone distilled off and the residue extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was separated by treatment with 7% aq. sodium carbonate (100 ml), afforded the unchanged neutral starting material (1.62 g) and the half ester (2, 9.1 g), b.p. 200 °C/0.003 mm (Found : C, 64.1; H, 9.5. C₂₀H₃₆O₃ requires : C, 64.5; H, 9.7%).

threo-Isoaleuritic acid (3) : The above half ester (2, 2.0 g) in dry THF (25 ml) was reduced with LAH (0.4 g) under agitation and left overnight. The excess of LAH was destroyed with a few drops of water, treated with cold dil. HCl and extract was then extracted with NaHCO₃ (5%), which was acidified followed by deacetonation by boiling for 30 min and extracted with ethyl acetate. Removal of the solvent afforded the expected *threo*-isoaleuritic acid (0.8 g). It was recrystallised from EtOAc (m.p. 95–96 °C); ν_{max} 3250, 1720 and 1690 cm^{-1} (Found : C, 63.0; H, 10.7. Calcd. for C₁₆H₃₂O₅ : C, 63.1; H, 10.6%).

16-Hydroxy-(E)-7-hexadecenoic acid (4) : Compound 3 (3.08 g) was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane (25 ml), imidazole (2.20 g), chlorodiphenyl phosphine (3.28 g) and iodine (3.96 g) were then added with stirring, after 2 h the reaction mixture was diluted with water and washed with

aq. sodium thiosulphate (5%, 50 ml), followed by aq. Na₂CO₃ (5%, 50 ml). Sodium extract was acidified with 10% H₂SO₄ and its usual work-up with EtOAc furnished 4 as a solid, which was crystallised from benzene (2.8 g), m.p. 54–56 °C (lit.² m.p. 55–56 °C); ν_{max} 3250 (-OH), 1695 and 968 cm^{-1} (CH^(E)=CH) (Found : C, 71.2; H, 11.4. Calcd. for C₁₆H₃₀O₃ : C, 71.1; H, 11.2%).

Methyl-16-hydroxy-(E)-7-hexadecenoate (5) : The foregoing unsaturated acid (2.5 g) was esterified with dry methanol (30 ml) containing catalytic amount of BF₃.Et₂O on steam bath for 15 min. Usual work-up with ether afforded 5 as a liquid (2.3 g), which was purified by column chromatography using ether as eluent; ν_{max} 3250 (-OH), 1725 (C=O of ester carbonyl), 970 cm^{-1} (CH^(E)=CH) (Found : C, 72.0; H, 11.1. C₁₇H₃₂O₃ requires : C, 72.1; H, 11.2%).

Ambrettolide (6) : The above ester (2.2 g) was distilled with MgCl₂.6H₂O (0.2 g) at bath temperature of 270–280 °C/0.1 mm. The distillate (1.3 g) was dissolved in ether (50 ml) and washed with aq. Na₂CO₃ (5%, 50 ml). The ethereal extract washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent gave crude ambrettolide, which was redistilled b.p. 170–175 °C/2 mm (lit.² b.p. 170 °C/2 mm, yield 57.8%); ν_{max} 1731 (C=O in a macrocyclic lactone), 970 cm^{-1} (CH^(E)=CH); ^1H NMR : 1.32 (18H, br), 1.87 (4H, br), 2.25 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 4.1 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 5.3 (2H, br).

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